

The Adoption Journey of Active Learning Strategies: reflections from a Brazilian perspective

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15874371>

Abstract

Adopting active learning strategies can be a difficult decision, filled with apprehension and uncertainties. Various reasons for not adopting active learning strategies are found in the literature, such as fear of additional work, fear of students' reactions, and even concerns about peer evaluation. This paper proposes a discussion on the adoption journey of active learning strategies by a group of Brazilian engineering professors. Therefore, it presents reflections that originated from a focus group session organized by the Working Group on Active Learning in Engineering Education (GTAAEE), held in 2023, during the 51th Brazilian Congress of Engineering Education (COBENGE). The adoption journey of active learning strategies in engineering education developed during the focus group session draws inspiration from a customer journey concept. This paper describes how educators progress through phases such as learning and discovery, recognizing opportunities, considering active learning strategies, adopting these strategies, and eventually publishing their experiences. Additionally, the paper presents the participants' positions within this journey and describes the emotions they experienced, revealing a mix of excitement, fear, loneliness, and eventual awareness of their capacity to balance traditional and active learning strategies. These reflections underscored the non-linear and often overlapping nature of the process, as educators might simultaneously explore new strategies while consolidating others. This paper also discusses key challenges and needs on the adoption of active learning strategies, including the demand for tailored materials, guidance from facilitators, financial support for infrastructure, and more opportunities for collaboration and exchange with peers. This reflection emphasizes the importance of adequate spaces for interdisciplinary dialogue and specific conferences on educational methods to foster a sense of community and encourage engineering education research. The insights of this paper can be explored to create content, to organize events, and to propose actions aimed at supporting educators in overcoming the challenges of adopting active learning strategies in engineering education.

Keywords: Active Learning; Training; Engineering Education

1 Introduction

The adoption of active learning strategies in engineering education is a phenomenon influenced by multiple factors, including governmental guidelines, institutional directives, curricular plans, and broader cultural and contextual aspects. At an international level, initiatives such as the Bologna Process have emphasized student-centered learning approaches, fostering a shift towards more interactive and participatory teaching methodologies. Similarly, in Brazil, the National Curricular Guidelines for Engineering Education (Brasil, 2019) highlight the importance of pedagogical strategies that encourage critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaborative learning, reinforcing the need for active learning in engineering education.

Beyond regulatory frameworks, institutional policies are attempt to foster the implementation of active learning strategies (Grimes & White III (2015). University mandates, pedagogical course plans, and faculty development programs are organized to create an environment conducive to the adoption of innovative teaching methodologies (Eickholt et al., 2019). Nevertheless, cultural and contextual factors—such as resistance

to change, professors fixed mindset (Aragon, Eddy & Graham, 2018), workload concerns (Michael, 2007), and the prevailing perception of traditional lecture-based teaching (Bordel, Alcarria & Cira, 2024) also are some barriers that decrease educators' willingness to embrace active learning practices (Guedes et al., 2023).

The objective of this paper is to present the findings of a focus group session conducted with engineering professors attending the 51st COBENGE conference in 2023. The discussion aimed to explore the adoption journey of active learning strategies, uncovering the motivations, challenges, and emotional experiences associated with this transition. By analyzing participants' perspectives, the study seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of the factors that facilitate or hinder the integration of active learning strategies in engineering education.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 provides a theoretical discussion on the adoption of active learning strategies; Section 3 outlines the methodological procedures used in the study; Section 4 presents and discusses the results of the focus group session; Section 5 offers the conclusions drawn from the study; and finally, Section 6 contains the references that support this research.

2 Adoption of Active Learning Strategies in Higher Education: an overview

The adoption of active learning strategies has proven to be increasingly effective, particularly when aligned with learning objectives (Gianesi, Massi & Mallet, 2021) and the need to develop higher-order skills in Bloom's taxonomy (Krathwohl, 2002). These strategies promote meaningful learning (Ausubel, 1968) and encourage students to actively engage in the construction of knowledge (Vygotsky, 1991), fostering complex cognitive skills such as analysis, evaluation, and creation. These competencies are essential for preparing professionals who are not only critical thinkers but also capable of solving real-world problems, especially in engineering—a field that demands not only technical expertise but also the ability to navigate interdisciplinary and innovative challenges (Campos, Pinto & Júnior, 2024).

Despite strong evidence supporting the benefits of active learning methodologies, their adoption faces significant resistance, particularly in engineering education (Grimes & White III, 2015; Eickholt et al., 2019; Aragon, Eddy & Graham, 2018; Michael, 2007; Bordel, Alcarria & Cira, 2024; Guedes et al., 2023). Traditional teaching, which remains predominant in higher education institutions, centralizes the learning process on the instructor, emphasizing linear and predictable content delivery. When instruction shifts to a student-centered approach using active methodologies, instructors may lose predictability in their lessons and direct control over the learning process (William, 2007; Gianesi, Massi & Mallet, 2021). This shift can create uncertainty and resistance, as active teaching requires greater flexibility, continuous adaptation, and a growth-oriented mindset (Aragon, Eddy & Graham, 2018).

The literature identifies several barriers to adopting active learning (Bordel, Alcarria & Cira, 2024). Among these, faculty members' negative perceptions stand out, such as concerns over increased workload and the fear of being perceived by peers as "not working" when implementing these strategies (Guedes, 2023). Additionally, a lack of knowledge about active learning methods and their practical application further contributes to resistance, as many instructors do not feel adequately prepared to use these strategies effectively, leading to a disconnect from innovative pedagogical approaches (Eickholt et al., 2019). Moreover, physical space limitations and a lack of institutional support are also cited obstacles (Guedes et al., 2023).

Silva (2020) understands that, for active methodologies to be effective, it is important that the educator is prepared to modify their teaching and learning concepts, allowing for new ways of interacting with knowledge

and innovative solutions to activities. It is emphasized that perhaps the most difficult change to assimilate is the awareness that certain parts of the content may be sufficient to solve specific problems, while other parts may not be addressed. This rigidity on the part of the professional is also a barrier to the broader and correct use of active methodologies.

William (2007) outlines key barriers to implementing active learning, which are supported by various authors. These barriers can be categorized into student, teacher, and pedagogical challenges. Students often struggle with how to engage in active learning, lack preparation, show reluctance to participate, or demonstrate varying levels of maturity. Teachers face difficulties related to the time required for lesson planning, reduced classroom control, negative perceptions from colleagues, and concerns about student evaluations. From a pedagogical perspective, factors such as inadequate classroom setups, insufficient class time, challenges in assessing students, large class sizes, and unpredictable learning outcomes make active learning harder to implement.

Understanding the variables that influence the adoption of active methodologies in engineering education is essential to overcoming these barriers. Resistance to student-centered teaching and the lack of pedagogical training among faculty directly impact the implementation of these strategies. To effectively promote active learning, it is crucial to establish well-structured faculty training programs and institutional support mechanisms that empower instructors to confidently adopt new pedagogical approaches. This, in turn, fosters the comprehensive development of students, better prepares them for professional challenges, and ensures alignment with curricular guidelines and the evolving demands of the job market.

3 Materials and Methods

This study employs a qualitative, exploratory research design based on a focus group methodology (Krueger & Casey, 2015). Exploratory research is particularly suitable for investigating complex, underexplored phenomena, as it enables researchers to gain insights into participants' perspectives and lived experiences (Stebbins, 2001). A qualitative approach facilitates a deeper understanding of social processes by fostering interactions among participants who share common experiences and concerns related to a specific topic (Krueger & Casey, 2015). Given these advantages, the focus group methodology was selected to explore the challenges and motivations behind the adoption of active learning strategies (Krueger & Casey, 2015).

The focus group session took place on September 18, 2023, during the COBENGE 2023 conference, as part of the Working Group on Active Learning in Engineering Education (GTAAEE). Participants included GTAAEE members and 10 additional attendees representing various Brazilian higher education institutions, such as the Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, the Aeronautics Institute of Technology, the Federal University of São Carlos, the Federal University of Pará, the Federal University of Itajubá, and the Federal Institute of Espírito Santo. Out of 10 participants, 7 answered the questions made by the focus group organizers.

The session focused on the theme "Adoption Journey of Active Learning Strategies and Methods – Reflections and Proposals for GTAAEE." A structured activity was conducted to identify the different phases of the adoption journey experienced by faculty members and to generate proposals for GTAAEE's future initiatives (2023-2024). The discussion was inspired by the concept of the customer journey, as defined by Lemon and Verhoef (2016). This concept, originally from the Design Thinking approach, maps the experiences consumers have with a brand, from initial awareness to post-purchase engagement.

Based on the customer journey framework by Lemon & Verhoef (2016), which includes five phases—awareness, consideration, acquisition, service, and loyalty—the GTAAEE professors developed a five-phase journey for adopting Active Learning Strategies (ALS). By reflecting on their own experiences in adopting ALS, these professors outlined the typical behaviors that can occur at each phase of the journey. The design of the journey,

resulting from the discussions and reflections of the GTAAEE members, led to the phases described in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Proposed Adoption Journey of Active Learning Strategies

The proposed Adoption Journey of Active Learning Strategies (ALS) begins with Learning and Discovery, where professors recognize the need to improve their teaching practices. In the Recognition of the Opportunity phase, they identify the limitations of traditional methods and acknowledge the potential of ALS to address these gaps. In the Consideration of ALS phase, professors research various strategies, exploring how they can enhance student engagement and learning outcomes.

Once convinced, professors enter the Adoption of ALS phase, where they implement active learning strategies in their lessons. Finally, in the Publications on ALS phase, professors share their experiences through research and publications, contributing to the academic community and encouraging others to adopt similar approaches. This journey reflects a continuous process of learning, applying, and sharing innovative teaching practices.

Participants were first introduced to the proposed adoption journey of active learning strategy. They were then asked to reflect on their adoption journeys and identify the phase they perceived themselves to be in. Additionally, they were invited to discuss the emotions associated with their experiences, highlighting the complexities and non-linear nature of the adoption process.

Following this discussion, participants were asked to outline their key needs and challenges in adopting active learning strategies. Their responses provided insights into essential support mechanisms, such as access to facilitators, contextualized teaching materials, financial resources for infrastructure, and greater opportunities for collaboration and knowledge exchange among educators.

The data collected during the session were recorded, transcribed, and analyzed qualitatively to identify recurring themes and patterns. This methodological approach ensures a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing the adoption of active learning strategies, while also guiding the development of targeted initiatives to support engineering educators.

4 Results Discussion

As a result of the focus group organized by the GTAAEE, it was possible to identify three groups of information: 1) the stage of the adoption journey of ALS each participant reported he/she is; 2) the predominant emotions participants have about adopting ALS and 3) the need of support the participants report aiming to generate proposals for GTAAEE's initiatives for the 2023–2024 period.

After the Proposed Adoption Journey of Active Learning Strategies (Figure 1) was presented to the participants, they were asked to identify which stage of the journey they believed they were in and what emotions they

experienced throughout their adoption of AAEE. Table 1 summarizes the accounts collected from seven participants who voluntarily shared the stages of the journey they identified with.

Based on the participants' accounts, it was evident that most respondents perceive themselves as being in multiple stages of the adoption journey of ALS. After a collective discussion, participants agreed that this journey is a cyclical process, with parallel and non-linear phases. In other words, the same professor may simultaneously be discovering a new strategy, considering the adoption of another, and already implementing others. Among the seven respondents, two reported being in an advanced stage of the journey, where they are already able to generate publications on the adoption of ALS

Table 1: Respondents Adoption Journey of Active Learning Strategies Phase - Meeting GTAAEE 2023

Respondents	Learning and discovery	Recognition of the Opportunity	Consideration of ALS	Adoption of ALS	Publications on ALS
1	x		x	x	x
2			x	x	
3	x	x	x	x	x
4			x		
5			x		
6				x	
7	x	x			

Regarding the emotions experienced by respondents throughout their journey, the following situations were reported, as illustrated in the excerpts below:

"I feel both excitement and fear that it won't work." (Respondent 1)

"I feel like I'm alone in a rough sea; it's a solitary job." (Respondent 2)

"In the beginning, I was scared." (Respondent 3)

"I feel aware of what I am doing." (Respondent 4)

"Over time, I understood that it's not about doing everything, but rather integrating what I can into certain content. Some aspects can remain traditional." (Respondent 5)

"Euphoria and fear that it won't work—I don't know how the students will react." (Respondent 6)

As reported by the participants, there is a mix of emotions due to the uncertainty that ALS adopters experience. Many expressed fear and insecurity when facing the challenges of implementing active learning strategies, which leads to a demand for support in overcoming these obstacles.

In response to these concerns, participants were asked what specific needs related to their adoption journey of ALS they would like to bring to GTAAEE. The following demands were identified:

- **Access to facilitators who can assist teachers in moments of doubt** – Professors need knowledgeable mentors or facilitators who can provide guidance and support when they encounter challenges in implementing active learning strategies.
- **Access to materials contextualized by subject or discipline** – Teaching resources should be tailored to specific academic fields, making it easier for educators to integrate active learning into their subject areas effectively.
- **Financial support (e.g., alumni funding) to invest in infrastructure and other needs** – Adequate funding is necessary to improve classroom setups, acquire essential teaching tools, and support other logistical requirements for active learning implementation.
- **Help in dealing with curriculum constraints** – Faculty members require assistance in adapting their courses to accommodate active learning while ensuring alignment with institutional and accreditation requirements.
- **More opportunities for exchange on artistic learning approaches** – Educators seek spaces to explore and share methodologies that integrate artistic and creative approaches into active learning.
- **More spaces for interaction and collaboration among educators** – Professors benefit from structured environments where they can exchange experiences, discuss best practices, and collaboratively address challenges in active learning adoption.
- **Dedicated spaces within subject-specific conferences for education-related work** – Conferences in specialized fields should include dedicated sessions or tracks for discussions and presentations on active learning practices within those disciplines.
- **Access to a learning community to discuss and publish together** – A supportive network of educators can facilitate knowledge sharing, collaborative research, and joint publications on active learning strategies and their outcomes.

Through the interactions in this meeting, it was possible to hear the academic community's expectations regarding ALS adoption. These insights were used to generate content, organize events, and shape GTAAEE's proposed initiatives. These inputs were used to organize a traveling Brazilian symposium, designed to give professors from different regions the opportunity to participate in the events. Additionally, the group has an established practice of annually producing articles and book chapters on the topic. As a future initiative, online content will also be made available through live sessions on the GTAAEE YouTube channel, further expanding support for educators across Brazil. All interaction opportunities are announced via the GTAAEE Instagram, to provide followers with valuable information to assist them on their journey.

5 Conclusion

The findings from this study highlight the complex and dynamic nature of adopting active learning strategies in engineering education. The data collected from the focus group demonstrate that this process is not linear; rather, it involves overlapping phases in which educators simultaneously explore, consider, and implement various methodologies. The emotions reported by participants reinforce the idea that this journey is marked by both enthusiasm and apprehension, with fear and uncertainty often accompanying the transition from traditional to active teaching approaches. Such emotions emphasize the need for greater institutional support, structured professional development, and peer collaboration to ease the adoption process.

Moreover, the barriers identified—ranging from curriculum constraints to the lack of context-specific materials and financial limitations—point to systemic challenges that must be addressed for active learning strategies to be effectively integrated. The expressed need for facilitators, collaborative spaces, and tailored resources

underscores the importance of fostering a strong learning community where educators can exchange experiences, refine their practices, and collectively advance pedagogical innovation.

By incorporating these insights, initiatives such as GTAAEE's traveling symposium, academic publications, and online content creation serve as crucial mechanisms to support faculty in their adoption journey. The continued dissemination of knowledge and expansion of interactive spaces will be essential in ensuring that active learning methodologies are not only embraced but also sustained in engineering education. Addressing these challenges through structured support systems will empower educators, enhance student learning experiences, and contribute to a broader transformation in higher education.

It is important to highlight the limitations of this research. First, this research relied on self-reported data from a relatively small group of participants, which may not fully capture the diversity of experiences and challenges faced by educators in different institutional contexts. Another constraint is the absence of longitudinal data to assess the long-term impact of active learning adoption on teaching practices and student outcomes. Future research should aim to expand the sample size, incorporating a broader range of institutions and disciplines to better understand the factors influencing active learning implementation. Longitudinal studies tracking educators over time could provide deeper insights into how support mechanisms, training programs, and institutional policies affect the sustainability of these strategies. Further exploration into student perspectives on active learning adoption could also offer a more comprehensive view of its effectiveness and potential areas for improvement.

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